

Comparative Study of Competitive Anxiety and Self-concept Among Sprinters, Jumpers and Throwers of all India Inter-University Levels Athletes

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Abstract

The objective of the study was to compare the competitive anxiety and self-concept among sprinters, jumpers and throwers of All India Inter-University Levels Athletes. Total 45 male athletes participating in All India Inter-University were selected as subject for this study. The age of subject ranged between 18 to 25 years. The competitive anxiety and self-concept questionnaire prepared by Reiner Martens and Raj Kumar Saraswat was used to collect data to measure the level of competitive anxiety and self-concept. One way analysis of variance was used as a statistical procedure. The comparison of competitive anxiety and self-concept between sprinters, jumpers and throwers of All India Inter-University Levels Athletes. Competitive anxiety, and self-concept were not significant at 0.05 level.

Keywords

Self-Concept, Competitive Anxiety, Sprinters, Jumpers and Throwers

1. INTRODUCTION

Anxiety is a physiological response to a real or imagined threat. A certain amount of anxiety is needed for peak performance. But higher level of anxiety physically inhibits performance by causing muscular tension and disturbing coordination of the movement's therefore it is very important aspect to be handled. It highly helps a coach to prepare the athletes physically and mentally in such away that he himself is able to resist and tolerate any kind of psychological eventually, which may occur before or during the competition. Among all the various sports events present no doubt track and field has the maximum utilization of mechanical theories. Track and field get the popularity because of it's similarly with daily life doing.

In competitive sports Psychologist preparation of an athlete or a team is as much important as technique of the different skills of the game on a specific line. In modern competitive sports, the athletes and teams are prepared not only to play the game and for winning the game it is not only the proficiency in the skills, which bring victory but more important is the mental preparation. The spirit and the attitudes of the athletes with which they play and perform the best in the competition (Singh, 1992).

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objective of the study was to compare competitive anxiety and self-concept among sprinters, jumpers and throwers of All India Inter-University Levels Athletes.

3. METHODOLOGY

The subjects for the study were 45 male players participating in All India Inter-University Athletics Championships 2014–15 were selected as subject for this study. The age of subject ranged between 18 to 25 years. The competitive anxiety and self-concept questionnaire prepared by Reiner Martens and Raj Kumar Saraswat was used to collect data to measure the level of competitive anxiety and self-concept. The comparison of competitive anxiety and self-concept between sprinters, jumpers and throwers.

The competitive state anxiety inventory-2 (CSAI-2) by Rainer Marties selected for the study because it is sports specific anxiety test. The test was administered to the subjects at Inter-University competition. The subjects were assembled in different groups. Clear instructions were specifically given to the subjects that all the items in the questionnaire must be attempted. The CSAI-2 s scored by computing a separate total for each of the three sub scales with score ranging from a low of 9 to a high of 36. Number of total score for the inventory is computed. The CSAI-2 consists of 27 items. Each item is keyed with following response option and score Not at all = 4, Somewhat = 3, Moderately = 2, Very much = 1. The various state anxiety subscale namely somatic tension, cognitive worry and self-confidence is attained by summing up 9 scores each separately for all the sub scales. Inventories that are missing not more than one response per sub scale can still be scored but any inventory in which two or more items any one subscale are omitted should be invalidated. to obtain sub scale scores when an item has been omitted and computed the mean item score for the right answer items, multiplying this value by 9 and then round the product to the nearest whole number.

The self-concept inventory provides six separate dimensions of self-concept, viz. physical, social, temperamental, educational, moral and intellectual self-concept. It also gives a total self-concept score. Each item was provided with five alternatives. Responses are obtained on test booklet itself. There was no time limit but generally 20 minutes were found sufficient for responding to all the items. The research scholar supervised the group and verify that they were responding in a desired way.

The respondent was provided with five alternatives to give his responses ranging most acceptable to least acceptable description of his self-concept. The alternatives or responses were arranged in such a way that the scoring system for all the items remained the same i.e. 5, 4, 3, 2, 1 whether the items were positive or negative. The summated scores of all the forty eight items provided the total self-concept of an individual. A high score on this inventory indicates a high self-concept, while a low score indicates a low self-concept. The various responses were received in terms of level of competitive anxiety and self-concept of sprinters, jumpers and thrower. ANOVA was applied to analysis the data. The level of significance will be fixed at 0.05 of confidence.

4. RESULTS OF THE STUDY

The data was analyzed by one way analysis of variance for the data or anxiety and self-concept between sprinters, jumpers and throwers of All India Inter-University male athletes has been shown in the Table 1.

Table 1: Analysis of Variance for the Data of Competitive Anxiety

Sources of Variance	Df	SS	MSS	F-ratio
Between Group	2	2.177	1.088	0.669
Among Group	42	68.266	1.625	

$F_{0.05}(2,42) = 3.22$

Since the value of the completed F-ratio for different positions (sprinters, jumpers and throwers) was lower than the tabulated F at 0.05 level as shown in table 1, therefore calculated F-ratio was significant and hypothesis for different position was rejected at 0.05 level.

Table 2: Analysis of Variance for the Data of Self-concept

Sources of Variance	Df	SS	MSS	F-ratio
Between Group	2	86.177	43.088	0.201
Among Group	42	90.74	214.019	

$F_{0.05}(2,42) = 3.32$

In the above Table, F-ratio for different positions (sprinters, jumpers and throwers) was lower than the tabulated F at 0.05 level there calculated F-ratio were significant. Thus hypothesis for different position was rejected at 0.105 level.

5. FINDINGS

Athletes are required to pay attention to perceive selective information by discriminating among cues and choose right movement pattern at right time. It is also evident from the concept of sprinters, jumpers and throwers where a athletes can move from according to the need of specific situation in the event this might be one of the reasons for a similar self-concept level in sprinters, jumpers and throwers (Bell Keith F. 1983).

This present study reveals that there is no significant difference in mean of competitive anxiety and self-concept among sprinters, jumpers and throwers.

The findings of study showed that sprinters, jumpers and throwers didn't differ significantly with respect to competition anxiety. Implying that state competition anxiety level of sprinters, jumpers and throwers were not of different level rather is of more or less same. This finding may be attributed the fact that, competition anxiety state formes situation specific apprehension about uncertainty in probable out comes of competition since both sprint, jump and throw are similar type of events as it of indivisual events, short duration and limited tempest based and hence the uncertainty of out come is may be because of limited options of attempt unlike other long duration etc. Record of the similarity in nature the evocation of pre competition state anxietyand self-concept amount sprinters, jumpers and throwers were of similar level (Silva John M. and Swinberg Robert, 1984).

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